

Incorporation of Zinc Doped Borate Bioactive Glasses into Soft Matrices for Wound Healing Applications

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ABSTRACT

Application of bioactive glasses in orthopedic and dental application, as well as bone tissue engineering gained a great interest in the last 50 years since its discovery by Hench et al. in 1971 [1]. Most frequently studied and well documented system for bone filling materials, dental application and bone implants bioglass are the compositions 455S (45% SiO₂, 24.5% Na₂O and CaO, 6% P₂O₅ by wt.) and 13-93 (53% SiO₂, 20% CaO, 12% K₂O, 6% Na₂O, 5% MgO, 4% P₂O₅). Recently boron containing glasses attracted attention for applications beyond bone and teeth: soft tissue applications including wound healing are also studied. Bioactive borate glasses show 5 times faster biodegradation and better bioactivity compare to silicate glass due to presence of silicate-rich layer [2]. Unlike the 45S5 silicate bioactive glass, they transform to hydroxyapatite (HA) completely. This feature originates from less stable structure of boron containing glasses with different type of glass forming units and lower network connectivity [3]. When considering all these properties, borate bioactive glasses can be pointed out as promising biomaterials for wound healing applications.

To provide ideal dressing for a wound, both natural environment and healing process needs to be mimicked. For this purpose, both natural and synthetic polymers can be applied. However, the polymers by themselves are insufficient in providing required mechanical strength, chemical reactivity, biocompatibility and bioactivity to mimic natural tissue. Their mechanical properties must be improved and optimized, and additional bioactivity must be provided by another component [4]. Borate glasses are one of the promising candidates for preparation of a biocomposite material which could provide temporary support for new tissue formation.

When the body cannot heal naturally, suitable stimulation is needed to enhance the healing process. This can be achieved by the use of biomaterials, which release suitable ions such as Ca, P, B etc. to the surrounding area. These ions have specific roles during hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation and tissue remodelling phases of wound healing. For example, Ca ions that is present in a BG composition as a glass modifier, can promote the migration of epidermal cells and accelerate formation of blood clot. Upon dissolution, silicate and borate bioactive glasses increase the local pH contributing to antibacterial effect. Bioactive glasses can be also doped with therapeutic ions such as Ag⁺, Cu²⁺, Ga³⁺ and Zn²⁺ with antibacterial properties, thus assisting and promoting the wound healing process[5].

In this study, 1393-B3 bioactive glass doped with zinc was produced by conventional melting. The compositions of prepared glasses are summarized in Table 1. In doped glasses Zn was added to substitute

calcium. The real composition of prepared glasses was verified by chemical analysis by optical emission spectroscopy in inductively coupled plasma (ICP-OES, VARIAN MPX), (Table 2). The real compositions of produced glass corresponds with the theoretical compositions. The X-ray powder diffraction data (2θ , range from 10 to 80), confirmed that produced bioactive zinc doped glasses were X-ray amorphous (Fig.1.).

Table 1. Composition of produced borate bioactive glasses

Mol%	1393B3	1Zn-1393B3	3Zn-1393B3	6Zn-1393B3
Na ₂ O	5.96	5.96	5.96	5.96
K ₂ O	7.91	7.91	7.91	7.91
MgO	7.66	7.66	7.66	7.66
CaO	22.15	21.15	19.15	16.15
B ₂ O ₃	54.75	54.57	54.57	54.57
P ₂ O ₅	1.75	1.75	1.75	1.75
ZnO	-	1	3	6

Table 2. ICP-OES result of produced bioactive borate glasses

Mol %	B ₂ O ₃	K ₂ O	MgO	Na ₂ O	CaO	P ₂ O ₅	ZnO
1393-B3	52.76±0.76	10.55±0.18	3.97±0.07	4.17±0.07	17.83±0.2	3.50±0.05	-
1Zn	51.51±1.42	10.25±0.28	4.15±0.10	4.06±0.09	17.34±0.4	3.55±0.12	1.10±0.02
3Zn	50.49±0.16	10.11±0.051	3.93±0.02	3.91±0.01	14.83±0.08	3.37±0.04	3.23±0.01
6Zn	52.40±3.03	10.93±0.17	4.28±0.04	4.21±0.09	13.80±0.40	3.70±0.11	7.16±0.16

Future work will include the studies of bioactivity and degradation of zinc doped glasses. In addition, Ga-doped borate bioactive glasses will be produced by conventional glass melting route and will be characterized in the same manner. Biocomposite fibres containing Ga and Zn doped bioactive borate glasses in polylactic acid polymeric matrix will be produced by electrospinning method as potential dressings for wound healing applications.

Keywords: Biocomposite, bioactive borate glass, wound healing.

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